

Single cell RNAseq analysis in R

22-23 August 2022

Material Name	Material Type (Format)	Description	URL/Persistent Identifier
scRNAseq_Schedule	Information (PDF)	Schedule for the workshop providing a breakdown of topics and timings	Included in this Zenodo record
scRNAseq Analysis in R with Seurat	Online tutorial (webpage)	Online tutorial on which this workshop is based. Tutorial theory, exercises and examples.	Available via https://swbioinf.github.io/scRNAseqInR_Doco/index.html
scRNAseq_Slides	Slides (PDF)	Slides used to introduce concepts during the workshop	Included in this Zenodo record
scRNAseq_Resources	Information (PDF)	A list of resources recommended by trainers and participants	Included in this Zenodo record
scRNAseq_QandA	Information (PDF)	Archive of questions and their answers from the workshop Slack Channel.	Included in this Zenodo record